

Examining Effects of Electronic Market Functions on Decrease in Product Unit Cost and Response Time to Customer

Authors : Maziyar Nourae

Abstract : Electronic markets in recent decades contribute remarkably in business transactions. Many organizations consider traditional ways of trade non-economical and therefore they do trade only through electronic markets. There are different categorizations of electronic markets functions. In one classification, functions of electronic markets are categorized into classes as information, transactions, and value added. In the present paper, effects of the three classes on the two major elements of the supply chain management are measured. The two elements are decrease in the product unit cost and reduction in response time to the customer. The results of the current research show that among nine minor elements related to the three classes of electronic markets functions, six factors and three factors influence on reduction of the product unit cost and reduction of response time to the customer, respectively.

Keywords : electronic commerce, electronic market, B2B trade, supply chain management

Conference Title : ICEID 2014 : International Conference on Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Development

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014